

A COMPARISON OF RENAL CALCULI: EVALUATING PREVALENCE, SIZE, AND LOCATION BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL PATIENTS.

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Abstract

Renal calculi represent a significant urological concern with varying prevalence across populations. This retrospective cross-sectional study, conducted over six months at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, involved 140 patients aged 10 years and above who underwent CT imaging for suspected renal calculi. The study assessed the prevalence, size, and anatomical location of kidney stones, comparing urban and rural populations. A higher prevalence was observed in rural patients (57.85%) compared to urban (42.14%), with males (66%) more affected than females (34%). The most impacted age group was 61–70 years (25%). Calculi were bilateral in 37.1% of cases, left-sided in 38.5%, and right-sided in 24.2%. Stone sizes most frequently fell into two categories: <4 mm (27%) and >10 mm (29%), indicating a bimodal distribution. The mid-pole of the kidney was the most common site of occurrence (37%). These findings underscore the need for targeted prevention, early detection, and region-specific public health strategies to manage renal calculi effectively.

Key words:

Renal calculi, kidney stones, prevalence, CT imaging, rural vs urban, stone size, anatomical location, urolithiasis.

Introduction

Kidney stones, also known as nephrolithiasis, form when urine becomes highly concentrated, leading to the crystallisation and aggregation of dissolved minerals such as calcium, oxalate, and uric acid¹. This supersaturated state often results from inadequate fluid intake, poor dietary habits, or specific medical conditions⁽¹⁾. The likelihood of renal calculi is greater in males than in females. This difference is attributed to a higher dietary intake of stone-promoting substances, elevated uric acid levels in men, and the function of testosterone in

promoting oxalate and calcium formation—key components of certain types of stones⁽¹⁾. The stones vary in size and composition, ranging from tiny granules to large pebble-like masses. Although they can also be found in the ureters and bladder, they usually localise in the renal tubules and collecting system⁽²⁾. Their appearance may be smooth or jagged and can range in colour from yellow to brown. Structurally, kidney stones consist of inorganic crystals embedded in an organic matrix that coats and fills the spaces between and within the crystals^(3,4).

Several metabolic conditions further contribute to stone formation, including cystinuria, gout, and hyperparathyroidism. Other risk factors include low fluid consumption, excessive or insufficient physical activity, obesity, certain types of weight-loss surgery, and diets rich in salt and sugar. Infections and genetic predispositions also play an important role in the development of nephrolithiasis⁽⁵⁾.

Kidney stones can be divided into four main categories, each associated with various risk factors and pathophysiological mechanisms. The most prevalent type of stones are calcium stones, often appearing in the form of calcium oxalate. These are typically linked with hypercalciuria resulting from hyperparathyroidism and may also involve conditions such as hyperuricosuria, hypocitraturia, hyperoxaluria, and hypomagnesuria⁽⁶⁾. Uric acid calculi usually form among patients with high-protein diets, gouty arthritis, or dehydration and are more likely to develop in acidic urine (pH ~5.5). They are frequently radiolucent, making them difficult to detect using standard X-rays^(7,8). Struvite stones, or infected stones, which are made of magnesium ammonium phosphate, usually appear when there are persistent urea-splitting urinary tract infections such as *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Klebsiella*⁽⁹⁾. Cystine stones are less common and occur in individuals with cystinuria, a hereditary condition that causes the kidneys to excrete excessive amounts of the amino acid cystine. These

stones can be difficult to detect via X-ray due to their high sulphur content⁽¹⁰⁾.

The clinical presentation of renal calculi is determined by the size and location of the stones and the presence of infection. Common symptoms include severe and sharp flank pain (often radiating to the lower abdomen), vomiting, haematuria, and foul-smelling or discoloured urine. Some individuals may also experience fever, urinary urgency, frequency, or dysuria. When a stone obstructs the ureter, it can lead to swelling of the kidney and ureteric spasms, resulting in intense and fluctuating pain^(11,12).

Multiple factors influence the development of renal calculi, such as age, sex, race, climate, and diet^(13,14). In recent years, dietary patterns have emerged as one of the most significant contributors to kidney stone formation. In developing countries like India, the shift toward high-sodium, processed foods and increased intake of animal protein has led to a rising incidence of obesity and metabolic syndrome, both of which are associated with increased risk of nephrolithiasis^(15,16). Calcium oxalate calculi remain the most frequently reported subtype in India. Additionally, systemic conditions including diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease have been associated with higher stone formation^(17,18). Rural populations may face greater risks due to limited access to healthcare, lack of awareness, and higher ambient temperatures that increase perspiration, reduce urine output, and promote crystallisation⁽¹⁹⁾.

Management of renal calculi is based on the size, concentration, anatomical location of the stones, and the severity of symptoms. Small renal calculi, typically less than 5 mm, may pass spontaneously with adequate hydration, generally requiring fluid intake of 2 to 3 litres per day. Larger stones or those causing obstruction or severe symptoms may require medical or surgical intervention. Common procedures include lithotripsy, which uses high-frequency sound waves to break stones into smaller fragments; percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL), a surgical method of removing major stones; and retrograde intrarenal surgery (RIRS), a less invasive procedure that employs a flexible fibre-optic ureteroscope^(20,21,22).

Preventive strategies are vital to reduce recurrence and include lifestyle modifications, dietary adjustments, and pharmacological treatments where necessary. Increasing daily water consumption to ensure a urinary output of at least 2 litres is a foundational preventive measure. Reducing the

intake of sodium and animal protein, maintaining an appropriate intake of dietary calcium, and avoiding oxalate-rich foods—particularly nuts, spinach, and chocolate—can significantly decrease the risk of stone formation. It is also essential to manage underlying conditions such as hyperparathyroidism and recurrent urinary tract infections⁽²³⁾.

Imaging plays a crucial role in the diagnosis and management of nephrolithiasis. Computed tomography (CT) scans are now considered the gold standard due to their high sensitivity and ability to identify even small stones. CT imaging provides essential details regarding stone burden, size, location, and associated anatomical abnormalities. The adoption of low-dose CT protocols has helped minimise radiation exposure while preserving diagnostic accuracy. CT scanning is not only vital for initial diagnosis but also plays a key role in treatment planning and post-operative follow-up^(24,25).

Methods

This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted over a six-month period at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan, with the objective of evaluating the prevalence, anatomical distribution, and size of renal calculi among patients from urban and rural backgrounds. A total of 140 patients aged 10 years and above, who presented with suspected renal colic or kidney stones, were included using purposive sampling.

The inclusion criteria comprised patients aged 10 years and older with clinical indications of renal calculi. Exclusion criteria included pregnancy or lactation, known allergy to contrast media, and presentation with trauma-related conditions.

Data were collected retrospectively from hospital records and radiological archives. Demographic variables such as age, sex, and residential status (urban vs rural) were recorded. Imaging was performed using a 128-slice Philips CT scanner. Stone characteristics—including laterality (right, left, bilateral), size (in millimetres), and anatomical location (e.g., upper pole, mid pole, lower pole, pelviureteric junction, vesicoureteric junction, ureter, bladder)—were assessed from CT images.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. All data were anonymised to ensure patient confidentiality, and informed consent was obtained prior to data use.

Results

URBAN/ RURAL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
URBAN	59	42.14%
RURAL	81	57.85%

Table 1

Out of 150 patients, 59 (42.14%) were from urban areas and 81 (57.85%) from rural areas. This indicates a higher representation of rural patients, suggesting possible disparities in healthcare access or disease prevalence between regions.

GENDER	TOTAL- 140	PERCENTAGE
MALE	92	66%
FEMALE	48	34%

Table 2

Among 140 patients, 92 (66%) were male and 48 (34%) were female. The data shows a higher prevalence of male patients, possibly indicating the condition is more common or more frequently diagnosed in males.

Figure 1

The age group of 61-70 is being the most represented at 25%. The 31-40 group followed at 16.4%, while the 81-90 group had the lowest representation at 1.4%. This suggests a higher prevalence of the condition among middle-aged and older adults.

Figure 2

The calculus sizes showed a bimodal distribution, with most being either >10 mm (29%) or <4 mm (27%). Sizes between 4-6 mm, 6-8 mm, and 8-10 mm accounted for 19%, 14%, and 11% respectively. This suggests peaks in both small and large calculus sizes among patients.

Figure 3

Among patients, 38.5% had left-sided calculi, 24.2% had right-sided, and 37.1% had bilateral involvement. This indicates a slightly higher occurrence on the left side, with a notable proportion showing bilateral presence.

Figure 4

The majority of calculi were located in the mid pole, accounting for 37% of cases, which was followed by

the lower pole with 26%. The upper pole was involved in 15% of patients. Calculi at the pelvic ureteric junction were seen in 10% of cases, while the vesicoureteric junction and mid ureter accounted for 6% and 3%, respectively. Less frequently, calculi were found in the pelvicalyceal system (2%) and bladder (1%). These findings suggest that the mid pole is the most common site of calculus formation.

AGE INTERVAL	SIZE OF CALCULUS (IN MM)
< 20	8.75 mm
21- 30	6.68 mm
31- 40	7.72 mm
41- 50	8.15 mm
51- 60	11 mm
61- 70	11.07 mm
71- 80	8.12 mm
81- 90	1.5 mm

Table 3

The average size of the calculus increased with age, peaking in the 61- 70 age group (11. 07 mm). It was lowest in the 81- 90 group (1.5 mm). Younger individuals (< 20) also showed relatively high levels (8.75 mm). After age 70, a sharp decline in calculus size was observed.

Summary of result

The study analysed 140 patients with renal calculi using CT imaging. The majority were male (66%) and from rural areas (57.85%), indicating a higher prevalence of stones among rural male populations. The most affected age group was 61–70 years, followed by 31–40 years, suggesting that middle-aged and older adults are more susceptible to kidney stone formation.

Analysis of stone laterality revealed that left-sided stones (38.5%) were slightly more common than right-sided stones (24.2%), while bilateral calculi were present in a substantial proportion of cases (37.1%).

Stone size exhibited a bimodal distribution, with stones measuring less than 4 mm observed in 27% of cases and those exceeding 10 mm in 29%, implying both early and delayed diagnoses within the population. The mid pole of the kidney was the

most frequently affected site (37%), followed by the lower pole (26%) and upper pole (15%).

The average stone size increased with age, peaking in the 61–70-year age group (11.07 mm), suggesting that stone burden may progress over time in the absence of early intervention.

These findings highlight notable disparities in terms of gender, age, and geographic location, as well as a tendency for larger stones and bilateral involvement among older and rural patients. The results underscore the importance of early screening initiatives and targeted health education programmes.

Discussion

The current study aimed to assess the occurrence, anatomical distribution, and size of renal calculi between urban and rural populations using computed tomography (CT) imaging. The results revealed notable demographic, geographic, and anatomical patterns that provide insight into the burden and presentation of kidney stones within the studied population.

The observed male predominance (66%) aligns with previous studies suggesting that men are more susceptible to nephrolithiasis. This may be attributed to higher urinary output of calcium and oxalate, differences in dietary patterns, and hormonal influences—particularly the role of testosterone in promoting oxalate formation. These findings are consistent with those of Kritika Gupta et al. (2024), who also reported a higher incidence of renal calculi among males⁽¹⁾.

Age-specific analysis indicated the highest prevalence of stones among patients aged 61–70 years, followed by the 31–40-year age group. This age distribution is consistent with studies by Mohammad Reza Safarinejad (2007) and Guohua Zeng et al. (2017), which found increasing stone prevalence with advancing age. Factors such as cumulative dietary exposure, reduced renal function, and the presence of comorbidities like diabetes and metabolic syndrome may contribute to this trend. The presence of larger stones in older individuals further supports the association between age and disease progression^(26,27).

Geographically, a higher proportion of patients were from rural areas (57.85%), suggesting a significant burden of disease in these populations. This contrasts with some reports that associate

urbanisation with increased stone formation due to processed diets and sedentary lifestyles. However, the rural predominance observed here may reflect limited access to healthcare, lack of early screening, and delayed diagnosis, all of which can result in more advanced disease at presentation. Environmental factors such as hot climates, low water intake, and physically demanding labour also contribute to increased calculi formation in rural settings.

The analysis of stone laterality revealed a slightly higher prevalence of left-sided stones (38.5%), although bilateral stones (37.1%) were also frequently observed. Bilateral involvement is clinically significant, as it may indicate systemic or metabolic conditions and highlights the need for comprehensive evaluation. This finding emphasises the importance of bilateral imaging in patients suspected of nephrolithiasis.

Stone size distribution exhibited a bimodal pattern, with the highest frequency observed for stones <4 mm (27%) and >10 mm (29%). This dual peak suggests two distinct clinical presentations: early detection of small, asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic stones, and late presentation of larger, potentially obstructive calculi. The higher incidence of large stones could reflect delayed health-seeking behaviour, particularly among rural patients.

With regard to anatomical localisation, the mid pole of the kidney was the most frequently affected site (37%), followed by the lower pole (26%) and upper pole (15%). Stones were also identified in the pelviureteric junction (10%), vesicoureteric junction (6%), ureter (3%), pelvicalyceal system (2%), and bladder (1%). These findings align with the known predilection of calculi to form in areas of the renal collecting system where urinary stasis may occur.

Importantly, average stone size increased with age, reaching its peak in the 61–70-year age group (11.07 mm). This trend supports the idea that longer duration of disease, inadequate fluid intake, and the absence of early interventions may result in stone growth over time.

Overall, these findings underscore the need for early detection, improved public awareness, and preventive healthcare strategies, particularly in rural settings. Encouraging increased fluid intake, promoting dietary education, and facilitating timely diagnostic imaging could substantially reduce the burden of renal calculi.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that renal calculi are more prevalent among males, individuals aged 61–70 years, and those residing in rural areas. The high incidence of bilateral stones and the bimodal size distribution—with a significant number of stones either very small or larger than 10 mm—suggest variations in disease detection and progression, potentially influenced by healthcare access and awareness. The mid pole of the kidney emerged as the most common site of stone localisation, and stone size was found to increase with age, emphasising the importance of timely intervention. These findings highlight the need for targeted public health measures, including early screening, hydration education, and dietary guidance, particularly for vulnerable rural and elderly populations. Enhanced awareness and accessible diagnostic services can play a critical role in reducing the clinical burden and complications associated with kidney stones.

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